

IMPREGNATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF PRE-IMPREGNATED COMMINGLED YARN AS NEW INTERMEDIATE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

Continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites have been attractive material system due to the recycle ability and secondary processing in recent years. However impregnation of thermoplastic resin into fiber bundle is difficult because of the continuous fiber and the high viscosity of matrix. In order to solve this problem, commingled yarn which was the intermediate material for CFRTP has developed [1]. Commingled yarn was the superior intermediate material in impregnation property and textile workability, but the miss alignment of carbon fiber was sometimes occurred in the composite made by commingled yarn because of shrinkage resin fiber in molding.

In order to solve this problem and to improve impregnation property and mechanical property of composite with commingled yarn, pre-impregnated commingled yarn (PCY) was developed. PCY is the new intermediate material which resin fiber of commingled yarn was melted but apportion of matrix was impregnated.

In this research, impregnation state and mechanical property of composite made from PCY and commingled yarn was investigated and compared. In impregnation state, it was clarified that PCY which was made from commingled yarn with melting its resin fiber enabled molding time shorter than commingled yarn with over 3 MPa. In mechanical property, it was clarified that PCY saved thermal shrink in heat compressing molding and increased mechanical property compare to commingled yarn.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite (FRTP) is paid attention. Thermoplastic resin gives composite secondary workability and recycling efficiency. Molding-cycle of FRTP is shorter than that of FRP, so that thermoplastic resin enables high-cycle-molding products. However, using continuous fiber and thermoplastic resin makes the impregnation difficult because of the high melt viscosity. According to this reason, intermediate material is important for molding FRTP, so commingled yarn set resin fiber nearby reinforcement fiber was developed by our team [1].

Commingled yarn was the superior intermediate material in impregnation property and textile workability, but the miss alignment of carbon fiber was sometimes effected in the composite made by

commingled yarn because thermal shrink of resin fiber in molding shrank carbon fiber. This problem was tried to solve by using commingled yarn whose resin fiber was pre-heated. It saved thermal-shrinkage in molding but a little thermal shrinkage was existed [2].

In order to solve this problem and to improve impregnation property and mechanical property of composite with commingled yarn, pre-impregnated commingled yarn (PCY) was developed. PCY is the new intermediate material which resin fiber of commingled yarn was already melted but a portion of matrix was impregnated. If all matrix was impregnated, it would become impregnated tape and it would too hard to use for textile but PCY whose a portion of matrix was impregnated easily to use for textile compare to impregnated tape.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impregnation property and mechanical property of composite made from commingled yarn and PCY.

2 MATERIALS

2.1 Commingled yarn

Fig. 1 shows the commingling machine used in the production of commingled yarn. Reinforcing fibers and resin fibers were sent out with each creel. Sent fibers were mixed with commingled unit. Then, the commingled yarn was completed by winding device, in which the volume fraction (V_f) of reinforcing fiber and resin fiber was about 50%, respectively. Pre-impregnated commingled yarn (PCY) was the yarn which a portion of matrix was impregnated and produced by this commingled yarn. In order to make PCY, cylindrical heater was set before winding device for melting resin fiber of commingled yarn. In this study, carbon fiber (T700SC-12K, TORAY) was used as reinforcing fiber, PA66 fiber (L235-35, Asahi kasei Fibers) was used as resin fiber. Each appearance and cross-sections of commingled yarn and PCY was shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3.

Fig.1 commingling machine.

Fig.2 Appearance (left) and cross-section in cylinder (right) of commingled yarn.

Fig.3 Appearance (left) and cross-section in cylinder (right) of PCY.

2.2 Unidirectional composite

In order to investigate the impregnation state and mechanical property of molding with two types of intermediate materials, unidirectional composites were fabricated. Fig. 4 shows the fabrication method of unidirectional composite. Fiber bundles were wound 12 times in a signal direction on metal flame. It was molded by heating and compression molding method and the molding temperature was 290 oC. Finally, unidirectional plate (20mm in width, 200mm in length) was molded and the cross-sectional observation and the tensile test were carried out. In this research, to investigate effects of molding condition on the impregnation state, unidirectional plates were molded with several conditions (molding time: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 min, molding pressure: 1, 3, 5, 7 MPa).

Fig.4 Fabrication and molding method of unidirectional composite.

3 EXPERIMENTS

In order to investigate impregnation state, un-impregnation ratio was defined. An example of cross-section of unidirectional plate was shown in Fig.5. In Fig.5, black area in cross-section was void called un-impregnation area. Un-impregnation ratio of composites was measured by using image analysis. The cross section of each molding was observed with the optical microscope. For the observation on cross section, the samples were emery grinded (#100~#2,000) and buffed (alumina particle, average particle size: 100 nm) after they were embedded in epoxy resin. After cross-sectional observation, un-impregnation ratio of each specimen was calculated. Un-impregnation ratio was defined as the area of un-impregnation area divided the area of cross-sectional area.

Tensile test was carried out under the conditions of 200 mm length, 100 mm distance between the grips, the test speed of 1 mm/min by using universal testing machine (INSTRON, Type4206).

Fig.5 Definition of un-impregnation ratio.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Impregnation state

From Fig.6 to Fig.9, relationships between un-impregnation ratio and molding time under the several molding pressure of 1, 3, 5, 7 MPa. In Fig.5, un-impregnation ratio of PCY in each time was higher than it of commingled yarn especially 1, 2 and 3 min of molding time. It was considered that PCY folded air because PCY is more bulky than commingled yarn, and the air was not ejected from bundle under 1 MPa of molding pressure. In Fig.6, Fig.7 and Fig.8, PCY had lower un-impregnation ratio compare to un-impregnation ratio of commingled yarn in each time. Un-impregnation ratio of commingled yarn was decreased linearly in all molding time but un-impregnation ratio of PCY was decreased linearly until 3 min of molding time and was kept after 3 min. According to this result, in the case of PCY, impregnation was finished in 3 min under 3, 5, 7 MPa. Compare to Fig.6 to Fig.8, in each molding time, un-impregnation ratio was decreased with increasing molding pressure. Compare to Fig.6, Fig.7, Fig.8 and Fig.9, un-impregnation ratio in each time under of Fig.6 1 MPa was higher than un-impregnation ratio of Fig.7 to Fig.9 under 3MPa to 7MPa especially in 1, 2 and 3 min. It suggested 1 MPa was low molding pressure for molding of commingled yarn and PCY. According to these results, it was clarified that PCY with over 3 MPa of molding pressure enabled high cycle molding compare to commingled yarn.

Fig.6 Relationship between Un-impregnation ratio and molding time (Molding pressure: 1 MPa).

Fig.7 Relationship between Un-impregnation ratio and molding time (Molding pressure: 3 MPa).

Fig.8 Relationship between Un-impregnation ratio and molding time (Molding pressure: 5 MPa).

Fig.9 Relationship between Un-impregnation ratio and molding time (Molding pressure: 7 MPa).

3.2 Mechanical property

The result of tensile test was shown in Fig.10. This specimen was molded in the condition of 5 min of molding time and 3 MPa of molding pressure because of having similar un-impregnation ratio under 0.5%. According to Fig.10, it was clarified that composites made from PCY and commingled

yarn had almost same elastic modulus and PCY was superior to commingled yarn in tensile strength. It was considered the effected to difference of un-impregnation ratio to difference of tensile strength was quite law because both un-impregnation ratio were similar and quite law. Surface pictures of unidirectional plate for tensile test were shown in Fig.11. According to Fig.11, it was observed that few miss alignment of carbon fiber in unidirectional plate made from PCY, so it was considered that tensile strength was increased because PCY whose resin fiber was already melted saved thermal shrink in heat compressing molding.

Fig.10 Mechanical properties of UD composites made from commingled yarn and PCY.

Fig.11 Surfaces of unidirectional plates (left: commingled yarn, right: PCY)

5 CONCLUSION

In this impregnation state, it was clarified that PCY which was made from commingled yarn with melting its resin fiber enabled molding time shorter than commingled yarn with over 3 MPa. In mechanical property, it was clarified that PCY saved thermal shrink in heat compressing molding and increased mechanical property compare to commingled yarn.

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